

PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS OF THE QUALITY OF ORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *This article states that primary school students, as noted in the state educational standard of primary general education, must independently organize the educational process. Therefore, today this category of children requires a special attitude in the learning process, since the growth of public knowledge in the framework of the study of information technology is realized quite quickly at the present stage of education. Studying the informational approach in the formation of media competence of younger students at the Russian language lessons at the general scientific level, teachers and scientists open up new opportunities for creating a coherent base for working with elementary school students using media tools in Russian language lessons, which will combine linguistics and media literacy.*

Keywords: *information technologies, methods of teaching computer literacy, information and communication technologies, formation, training, education.*

The main factor in updating vocational education is the need for the development of the economy and social sphere, science, technology, territorial labor markets, as well as the long-term needs of their development. In order to implement these requests, a system of constant monitoring of current and future labor market needs for personnel of various qualifications is necessary, including taking into account international trends. In accordance with these needs, it is necessary to build an optimal system of Russian education, and the main criterion for its dynamic development is the quality of educational programs and services. To achieve a new quality of education, the task of constructing effective mechanisms for forecasting the needs of the labor market and developing a system for effectively diagnosing the current state of the educational process is being updated.

Solving the problem of improving the quality of organizing the process of training specialists has a decisive impact on the effectiveness of the functioning and development of the integral educational system at the university and its constituent educational processes. At the same time, the highest quality organization of the educational process is recognized in which knowledge is acquired in the context of a model of future activity based on real life situations. Among the numerous quality problems, the key problem remains the diagnosis and assessment of the quality of education, since diagnostics is an obligatory component of any educational system. However, it is necessary not only to be able to diagnose the level of quality of education, but also to determine the conditions under which the required quality of education will be ensured [1].

The need to diagnose the quality of education arises due to the following circumstances. Firstly, the quality of education is the most important criterion for achievements in the scientific and practical spheres, so it is necessary to be able to diagnose it; secondly, diagnostics are necessary for understanding and formulating directions, paths and goals for the development of the educational space, creating “ideal” educational models; thirdly, the system itself, the diagnostic methodology, is valuable, primarily because it allows us to identify the conditions and pace of development of the student’s personality.

At the same time, in the field of pedagogical theory there is no comprehensive justification for pedagogical diagnostics as an integral component of the organization of the educational process at a university. There are practically no comprehensive descriptions of the experience of using diagnostic technologies and an integral system of diagnostic methods in the educational practice of universities. The above is explained by the poor development in pedagogical science of issues related to assessing the conditions for the effectiveness of the diagnostic procedures used and the results of their implementation in the practice of university education. The pedagogical design of diagnostic technologies has not found its worthy implementation in the light of new conceptual approaches to the modernization of Russian education. Mechanisms have not been developed that take into account the correlation of diagnosed performance indicators of subjects of pedagogical interaction with the potential properties of an organized pedagogical system, in particular with such as observability and identifiability. The capabilities of the problem-based approach to diagnosing the quantitative characteristics of the process of circulation of educational and cognitive information are not fully realized [2].

Some important questions for pedagogical theory were not raised at all, for example, questions about the influence of subjective and objective factors on the effectiveness of diagnosing the quality of the organized educational process at a university; on the development of technologies for integrating diagnostic tools into the system of organizing the educational and cognitive process at a university.

Consequently, on the one hand, pedagogical reality requires the development of effective models, tools and procedures for diagnosing the quality of the organization of the educational process, on the other hand, pedagogical theory is not yet able to adequately meet the ever-increasing demands of pedagogical practice [10].

The above allows us to formulate a number of fundamental contradictions that actualize the need to develop a holistic system of measures for pedagogical diagnostics of the quality of education at a university:

- between the need to promptly diagnose the quality of the organization of the educational process at a university and the presence of serious problems in determining adequate criteria for its quantitative and qualitative assessment;
- between the needs for the development of a system for diagnosing the quality of education and the lack of an integral scientifically based system of pedagogical diagnostics in the process of organizing the educational process at a university;
- between the objective need of higher education for modern theories of diagnosing educational processes and the low knowledge intensity of diagnostics, with the predominance of disorientation in the use of proven methods and procedures of diagnostic activity;

- between high requirements for subjects (teachers and students) of the educational process in terms of the quality of diagnostic (and self-diagnostic) activities and the low level of their qualifications in terms of ability to diagnose the educational process.

The totality of the noted shortcomings and highlighted contradictions allows us to synthesize the problem (of this study, which is to identify the theoretical, organizational and technological norms of pedagogical diagnostics required for the design and implementation in practice of universities of a system of diagnostic methods, methods and procedures necessary and sufficient to determine the quality indicators of the educational process at the university[9].

Pedagogical diagnostics of the quality of the organization of the educational process at a university is designed to solve, and indeed solves, many problems of pedagogy, including fundamental questions of pedagogical science: how to optimally correlate the dependence of the multi-level, knowledge-intensive organization of the educational process at a university with the peculiarities of the cognitive contents of activities and relationships to the knowable all participants in pedagogical interaction; how, in the conditions of pedagogical reality, to maximally “include” the individuality, uniqueness of the subjects of the educational process and direct it to improve the quality of education.

Diagnostics closes the entire cycle of organizing the educational space of a university. Moreover, without high-quality, scientifically based diagnostic mechanisms of the entire component composition of an organized system, including the activities of participants in pedagogical interaction, all organizational efforts may ultimately be reduced to “no” or lose their meaning [6].

Moreover, if we limit ourselves to collecting quasimetric data alone, then even minor problems of improving the quality of organization of the educational process cannot be solved. This is indisputable, but if they (the data) were not obtained through “trial and error”, but are based on a holistic (systemic), conceptual nature, then it can be stated that such diagnostics will provide: justification of teaching technologies in the conditions of teaching practice; creating for each student an information environment that adequately meets his needs and interests; differentiation of didactic teaching aids, taking into account the individuality of each subject of activity; achieving variability in the organization of the educational process, etc.

This is no longer just a set of specific data that reveals “some” qualitative aspects of the organized process, but scientifically-based, evidence-based facts that open up ways and identify mechanisms for improving the organization of the modern education system. Indeed, the construction of topological models within the framework of “model” and technological approaches to solving problems of diagnosing and assessing the quality of the organization of the educational process at a university expands the possibilities for improving its quality. Areas that reflect the advantages of such approaches include the ability to regulate the pace of students’ knowledge acquisition; expanding the forms of presenting their existing knowledge, emerging skills and abilities; consciousness in choosing alternative cognitive styles and providing them with adequate didactic means, which must be developed and presented by the organizers of the educational process [7].

Diagnostics opens a vision of the dominant components in the motivational space of the personality of students, forms an understanding that the development of motives, their filling with component composition is carried out under the influence of spontaneously arising impulses, and when creating the necessary conditions, they then form (transform) into stable interests and needs

with a tendency to the formation of a holistic motivational system of the student's personality. Moreover, the latter determines the direction of an individual's activity towards a particular activity and denotes not only the very fact of such activity, but also its effectiveness, as well as the qualitative features of its structure. At the same time, the considered "ensemble of properties" of the personality of a particular individual is a single whole, and only for the purpose of analysis it is advisable to isolate and diagnose its individual components, which are not autonomous entities isolated from each other. Moreover, these components together form a single system, the manifestations of which are found in the successful productive activities of subjects, for example, in the conditions of intra-university or post-graduate training [4].

A systematic approach to diagnosing educational activities at a university and organizing the entire educational process suggests that its qualitative manifestations at any stage of education are determined by students' psychographic ideas about the relevant professions, the attitudinal motivation for professional choice, dominant needs, perseverance, endurance, readiness, and general interest. , stability, typological: behavioral characteristics, etc. Knowledge of stable personal characteristics and characteristics inherent in students can be effectively used by subjects at various levels, subject to an attentive, unbiased, and generally professional attitude to the differences of each individual [8].

The conceptual essence and substantive characteristics of diagnostics and assessment of the quality of organization of the educational process at a university, through a) systematization of the stages of formation of pedagogical diagnostics; b) formalizing the essential differences between psychological and pedagogical diagnostics, c) determining the place of diagnostic methods and procedures in the system of ensuring the quality of education at a university; d) integration of theoretical, technological and instrumental mechanisms and diagnostic procedures, which contain meaningful invariants, type-forming (model) properties and diagnostic principles; e) organizing, planning and coordinating the efforts of subjects of pedagogical interaction; f) concentration of funds and resources, balanced in time and satisfaction of participants in the educational process.

The conceptual apparatus of one of the key sections of modern pedagogical theory and educational practice, relating to the diagnosis and assessment of the quality of the educational process at a university, has been clarified, through systematization of approaches that reveal ways of development formations, pedagogical diagnostics; formalization of essential differences between psychological and pedagogical diagnostics; defining its: functions;: systematization of stages, as well as principles of use, educational practice of universities[11].

The possibility of a rational, flexible use of a technological approach to organizing the educational process has been established, the logical consequence of which should be the skill of the teacher (and leader) to orient the educational process organized by him to its full success; the ability to co-organize and direct the efforts of all participants in pedagogical interaction in the right direction, so that each of them brings stability and qualitative certainty to the system; the ability to create conditions and make the necessary changes in them that impart the desired warmth and frankness to interpersonal relationships; the teacher's ability to concentrate available psychophysiological, professional and material (technical) resources to solve emerging problems or problematic situations; continuous development by the subject of pedagogical practice of his "integral characteristics" (Mitina JI.H.'s term) - orientation, competence, emotional flexibility.

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A model for diagnosing the quality of the organization of the educational process at a university has been developed, which includes five independent and, at the same time, interdependent invariants (sub models) - a normative sub model (including the requirements of normative documents that determine the level and quality of a specialist's professional training), a sub model of a specialist's activity (reflects the requirements for fundamental, theoretical, special and applied training, significant professional qualities of a university graduate), sub model of the academic discipline (includes educational goals, features of a professionally oriented system of knowledge, skills and abilities, degree and depth of study of the subject area, information capacity and didactic requirements and the fact that this sub model can be implemented within the framework of the didactic complex of information support for the educational process), the sub model for managing the learning process (takes into account the peculiarities of the teacher's implementation of the didactic capabilities of the diagnostic methodology he has developed; the source and type of guiding influence both on the entire educational process and on each student), the student's sub model (represents a certain reduction of the student's personality, which allows the teacher to diagnose and take into account in his teaching activities the socio-psychological qualities of the student, his level of readiness for work, for example, with information means, the level of basic and current knowledge, skills and abilities that characterize his educational and cognitive activity, the dynamics of the formation of significant professional qualities) and the sub-model of the teacher (takes into account the personal characteristics of the teacher himself - professional pedagogical qualities, depth of knowledge of the subject area, his information culture) [6].

Organizational and pedagogical conditions have been identified and systematized (the presence of a certain action on the part of the subjects of pedagogical interaction in the structure of the selected diagnostic model; the presence of a system of transferring the diagnosed process from one state to another - given; the presence of a oriented action on the part of the subjects of pedagogical interaction that is adequate to the goal; knowledge of the structural and functional composition of the selected action with a mandatory assessment of the results obtained; the presence of operational control over the dynamics of changes in the main components of the diagnosed process) increasing the efficiency of diagnosing the quality of the organization of educational and cognitive activities of students, which provide methodological and instrumental grounds for developing technology for the direct use of pedagogical diagnostics in the assessment process quality of university education[4].

A system of methods for diagnosing the personal and professional qualities of future specialists has been developed, consisting of methods for diagnosing readiness for professional

activity, the formation of personal qualities of students, the motivational characteristics of students, the formation of diagnostic skills, the formation of methods of cognitive activity, which is necessary and sufficient to solve the problems of diagnosing the quality of an organization educational process, the implementation of which closes the entire cycle of pedagogical diagnostics of the organization of the educational process at the university. This system of methods reflects the advantages of such approaches as the ability to regulate the pace of students' knowledge acquisition; expanding the forms of presenting their existing knowledge, emerging skills and abilities; consciousness in choosing alternative cognitive styles and providing them with adequate didactic means, which must be developed and presented by the organizers of the educational process.

Factors influencing the effectiveness of pedagogical diagnostics of the quality of the educational process at a university have been identified and systematized in order to construct a holistic picture of the phenomenon being diagnosed: consistency and orderliness in the organization of activities to assess the quality of the educational process; the presence of meaningful technology for organizing the actions performed and information on their effectiveness; activity and productivity; efficiency and clarity of diagnosis and quality assessment; managerial competence, organizational productivity, as well as psychological and organizational involvement in the work of subjects of the educational process.

A system of educational tasks has been developed, in which the possibilities of complex diagnostics of the organization of educational activities as an integral system are realized, while the component composition of the educational task and its functions are clarified; a classification matrix of tasks has been developed, which reveals the purpose of each task, the factors and mechanisms involved in solving it and assessing the quality of the solution results at each of its stages.

A technology has been developed for the step-by-step implementation of diagnostic procedures and techniques in the system of organizing the educational process at a university, the technological map of which includes a description of the essential features and causes of the diagnosed problem, a description of the model of the diagnosed process, the establishment of norms and boundaries for the activities of subjects of pedagogical interaction, the choice of approaches and methods for solving diagnostic problems, choosing a style for solving diagnostic problems, meeting the requirements for consistency of target settings and the actual results obtained in solving diagnostic problems, predictive analysis of the results obtained.

A system of indicators has been structured (the degree of development of general and professional skills, readiness for further training, the level of development of the motivational aspects of the individual, the desire for the most complete self-realization, taking into account the students' own abilities, their psychological portrait), criteria (which reflect quantitative indicators of the organization of the educational process; give an idea of the depth and strength of the processes occurring in the student's personality; determine the motives of behavior and action; show the stability over time of knowledge, abilities, skills, personality traits of the future specialist) and principles (distribution of resources for diagnostic operations, rationality, compliance, with the necessary diversity of subjects, time scaling, integration, parallelism of several diagnostic operations, their adaptation to the organization process) together forming components of the quality of the organization of the educational process, presented in the form of a matrix, along the vertical of which significant professional qualities of a specialist are indicated (factors of

professional activity, the need for which is determined by the requirements of the State Standards (HPE), horizontally, in percentage terms, the required level of their formation among university graduates.

The conducted theoretical and experimental studies allow us to conclude that the put forward research hypothesis has been confirmed, its reliability has been established in the process of testing and introducing the results of the work into the educational practice of higher professional schools, which have shown that the developed theoretical and empirical basis for pedagogical diagnostics, its technological support allows implement a qualitatively new approach to building mechanisms for organizing the educational process at a university, studying the dynamics of the functioning and development of each of its functionally significant components, namely: approaching the construction of the structure and content of activity subsystems of an integral pedagogical system from the point of view of their controlled design.

Research. In particular, there is an urgent need to develop educational and methodological materials of a diagnostic nature. The issues of integration and correlation between pedagogical science and pedagogical innovation in relation to diagnostic activities remain unresolved; further improvement of the conceptual and terminological apparatus for diagnosing the quality of organization of creative activity of subjects is required; current tasks are related to the study of psychological factors that influence the mechanisms of cognitive activity and allow them to be diagnosed; it is necessary to search and develop criteria for selecting new methods, organizational forms and content of diagnostic activities, create new objective criteria and methods for diagnosing the quality of education that are accessible to the teacher.

REFERENCES

1. Aetdinova P.P. Pedagogical diagnostics of levels of training as a condition for choosing teaching technologies (In the process of general education training of secondary school students). dis. .cand. ped. Sci. Kazan, 2001- 181 p.
2. Buknov A.E. Diagnostic algorithms. Ulan-Ude, 1976.39; Busygina: A.Jit. Organizational and pedagogical foundations of invariant training of higher professional teachers;; schools. Author's abstract. Dissertation: Dr. Ped. Sci. Tolyatti, 2000—36 pp.
3. Problems of modernization and improving the quality of professional training of specialists at universities: Monograph // Ed. T.F. Kryaklina. -Barnaul: AAEP Publishing House, 2004.
4. Djumayeva M.M. Didactic basis of implementation of the national curriculum Innovation in the modern education system March 2021 collections of scientific works Washington, USA 25th March 2021575-583
5. Djumaev M.I. The development of mathematical abilities in younger students. Science And Innovation International Scientific Journal Volume 2 Issue 1 January 2023 Uif-2022: 8.2 | Issn: 2181-3337 | Scientists. Uz/ 424-434
6. Djumayeva M.M. Teacher - student relationships in teaching natural sciences methodological preparation of future teachers. As a development factor Pedagogy of cooperation in improving the quality of education: international experience and modern approaches International scientific-practical conference, November 13, 2023 137-140
7. Djumaev M.I. Peculiarities of the unity and continuity of the national curriculum in teaching mathematics. THE MUGHALLIM IS ALSO QUITE KNOWLEDGEABLE. Scientific-methodological journal. ISSN 2181-7138 203 No. 1 314-324 Nökis

8. Djumaev M.I. Some Considerations of Teaching Mathematics Inuzbek Primary School. Journal of Mathematical & Computer Applications. SRC/JMCA-123. J Mathe & Comp Appli, 2023 Volume 2(2): 1-5 ISSN: 2754-6705
9. Teshaboev A. Yu. Pedagogist zharayon integral dynamic tizim sifatida //Journal of Science-Innovative Research in Uzbekistan. – 2023. – T. 1. – No. 7. – pp. 342-350.
10. Teshaboev A. Yu. Effectiveness of pedagogical diagnostics in school practice. Science and innovation international scientific journal volume 2 issue 11 november 2023 uif-2022: 8.2 | issn: 2181-3337 | scientists.uz 110-113.
11. Pidkasisty P.I. Organization of educational and cognitive activities of students. Textbook - M.: Pedagogical Society of Russia, 2004. -112 p.